

Chand Saudagar's Legacy: Unveiling the Allure of Manjusha Paintings

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Abstract

Manjusha, a decorated basket used in the Manasha Puja, is an integral part of the cultural heritage of Champanagar, Bhagalpur. The puja, significant during August, involves chanting verses that narrate the tragic tale of Behula and Lakhindar. This tradition, dating back 50-60 years, involved 20-30 families using locally sourced minerals to draw line diagrams on the Manjusha. Over time, these evolved into stylistic 2D figurines recognized as Folk Art. Champa, once the ancient capital of Anga, holds historical significance, referenced in texts like the Mahabharata and various Puranas. Its dynastic history is linked to Magadha, the Maurya, and Gupta dynasties, followed by the Pala Empire. Champa was a prominent trade city, highlighted in medieval tales like those of Chand Saudagar. The paintings on the Manjusha depict the Vishahari Gatha, detailing the legend of Goddess Vishahari and her interaction with Chando Saudagar. Traditional and modern styles of these paintings vary, with the former using simple, locally sourced colours, and the latter influenced by commercial art. The study of these paintings involves examining myths, rituals, and geographical contexts, providing insights into the historical and cultural significance of Champa. The Manasha Mangal and Vishahari Gatha share narratives of Behula's devotion and trials, emphasizing the rich folklore and religious practices of the region. This article aims to uncover the embedded history and cultural essence reflected in the Manjusha paintings and associated myths.

Key Words: Manjusha, Chand Saudagar, Champa, Mangal Kavya, Behula-Lakhindar.

Introduction:

Manjusha, in the local language, refers to a decorated basket made of light materialsⁱ used during the occasion of Manasha Puja (Figure 1.A). Locally known as Behula-Vishahari, this puja is particularly significant in the month of August (rainy season) when snakes frequently emerge due to water logging in their habitats. The themes of the paintings are derived from a *gatha* (verse) chanted during the Manasha (Vishahari) puja. About 50-60 years ago, the puja and the tradition of the paintings were concentrated in a specific area of Champanagar, Nathnagar, involving 20-30 families. At that time, the person offering homage to the Goddess would use colours from locally available minerals to draw line diagrams on the walls of the basket (Manjusha). These diagrams served as pictographic narrations of the *gatha*. After the puja, the basket was floated in the Ganga, commemorating the sad story of Behula-Lakhindarⁱⁱ. Over time, the style of narration has evolved. The original line drawings have transformed into stylistic 2D figurines created by local artists, now recognized as “Folk Art” or “Traditional Paintings.” Today, many institutions in the town promote these paintings, providing livelihoods for numerous artists.

Champa, the ancient capital of Anga, was a renowned city in ancient India, ruled by King Raja Lomapada. This historic capital has been identified with the large mound locally known as Karnagarh, located on the western edge of modern-day Bhagalpur town (Figure 1.B). The sanctity of Champa is highlighted in the Mahabharata, Matsya Purana, Padma Purana, and numerous other ancient scriptures. Its sacredness persisted at least until the time of Vidyapati and Queen Visvasadevi, who, in her Gangavakyavali, cites the Mahabharata to inform us that bathing in Champakathirtha would bestow the same merit as bathing in Manikarnika in Banaras. Additionally, near Champa were two other *tirthas*, Dandakhaya and Lalitika, also mentioned in the Mahabharata (Prasad 1987, 10-11).

**Figure 1.A: Decorated Manjusha
(Basket) made of Paper and
Bamboo sticks.**

The dynastic history of Anga, including Champa, is not well-documented. It is known that Champa was ruled by Dhatarattha and then Brahmadata before being annexed by Bimbisara of the Haryanka dynasty. Subsequently, it came under the direct rule of the Haryanka and Maurya dynasties of Magadha. After the fall of the Mauryas, the history of the region becomes unclear, but it regained prominence during the Gupta period. Therefore, the history of Magadha can be considered the history of Champa as well. Between the breakup of the Gupta Empire and the reign of Harshavardhana, Magadha experienced a period of struggle involving the Maukharis, the Gaudas, and the later Guptas. Political anarchy in Bihar and Bengal was ended in the mid-8th century with the election of Gopala as king, marking the beginning of the Pala dynasty. During the Pala period, Anga, including the Bhagalpur district, was an integral part of the dynasty. Murari's

Anargharaghava, from the later part of the 18th century A.D., refers to Champa as the capital of Gauda. This connection between Champa and the Pala kings of Gauda is inferred from the study of the Jayanagar image inscription. In the 11th century, Bengal and Anga suffered at the hands of Jatavarman, the founder of the Yadava dynasty of East Bengal. In the 12th century, a fierce war was fought between the kings of Gauda and Vanga, in which Sahura, the king of Champa, supported the king of Gauda. The famous Chinese traveller Xuanzang visited Champa in the 7th century. He described the town as being about 40 li in circumference, which means approximately 12 kilometres. He also detailed the city's walls, moat, and gates (Swarnkar 2007, 67).

Despite its significance as an early historic city, Champa has long been neglected by researchers. Champa was renowned for its trade, commerce, and river navigation, with numerous references to trade and craft guilds. According to Buddhist and Jain literature, it was a major business centre for jewellers (Sinha 1988, 96). In the medieval period, the story of the famous trader Chand Saudagar mentioned in various Mangal novels highlights Champa as a prominent trade city (Swarnkar 2007, 39-56). This story is elaborately found in the Manasha Mangal novel, first written by Kana Haridatta around the 13th century and subsequently retold by approximately 70 other writers (Dasgupta 1947, 20). Each writer added their own version, resulting in 70 different stories, making the original account vague and difficult to ascertain. The story of Chand Saudagar is one of the most famous legends in rural Bengal, centring on Champa. The city has been identified with various places, including Bardhaman, Tripura, Dhubdi, Bogura, Malda, Bhagalpur, and even Darjeeling, by local inhabitants. This diversity in identification is due to the many versions of the Manasha Mangal novels. Through this article, the authors attempt to throw a light in the process of identifying the location of Champa by examining traditional *gathas* (myths), the story of Manasha Mangal, and the paintings known by the inhabitants of Champanagar in the Bhagalpur district of Bihar. This approach aims to provide a clearer understanding of Champa's historical and cultural significance.

Figure 1.B: Location of the Campānagar (Yellow dot).

The Legends Depicted in the Paintings:

These paintings are deeply rooted in the *gatha*, which is also considered a mantra of the Manasha Puja (locally known as Vishahari Puja). The *gatha* begins with the belief that Lord Shiva, during his travels on earth with Parvati, built a shelter near the Sonadah tank in “Chaupaenagar”. Shiva would bathe in the tank, and one day, while bathing, five (or six, according to different tales) threads of hair came out of his locks and turned into beautiful flowers. He placed these flowers in his shelter and instructed Parvati not to touch them. However, Parvati ignored his instructions and touched the flowers, which instantly transformed into the five (or six) sisters of Goddess Vishahari. Parvati, not believing their story, insulted them. In retaliation, they bit her. After Shiva's request,

the sisters cured Parvati. Upon Parvati's recovery, Shiva, pleased, offered to grant the sisters a boon. They requested that they be worshipped on Earth. Shiva advised them to seek the devotion of Chando Saudagar, a prosperous trader from "Champanagari". If they could convince him to worship them, they would be worshipped by all. The Vishahari sisters went to the house of Chando Saudagar, who was then a prosperous trader in Champanagari. They narrated their story, but Chando Saudagar refused to worship them, dismissing them as frog-eating snake goddesses. Desperate, the Vishahari sisters killed six of his sons and destroyed his wealth by sinking his boat, yet Chando Saudagar still refused to worship them. His life became miserable; he lost his six sons and was reduced to poverty. Eventually, his wife Sonika gave birth to a son named Bala Lakhindra, and Chando Saudagar regained some of his wealth through his business. As Bala Lakhindra grew up, Chando Saudagar arranged his marriage with a beautiful girl named Behula from Ujani. Fearing the vengeance of the Vishahari sisters, Chando requested Vishwakarma to build a house of iron and bamboo with no holes. However, the Vishahari sisters threatened Vishwakarma, forcing him to leave a small hole in the house. On the night of the wedding, a snake bit Bala Lakhindra, causing his death, and leaving Behula a widow. Determined to bring her husband back to life Behula refused to dispose of his body and decided to go to heaven to plead for his life. She requested Vishwakarma to build a huge boat, which was decorated by a gardener named Lahsan. Behula began her journey from Gakul Ghat, passing through several ghats, such as Semapur, Vaagasaini, Bochasaini, Godasaini, Jeekasaini, Juarighat, and Shankheshar, eventually reaching "Netula Ghat". There she met Netula, a lady who washed the clothes of the gods. Behula persuaded Netula to let her assist in washing the clothes. Impressed by the brightness of the clothes washed by Behula, the gods allowed her entry to Devalok. Amazed by Behula's perseverance and chastity, the gods asked her to perform a dance. Her unique devotional dance pleased all the gods, who then asked her to seek a boon. Behula requested the lives of her husband, his six brothers, and all the drowned sailors, along with the restoration of all her father-in-law's wealth. The gods granted her requests, and the Vishahari sisters, accepting their defeat, again asked Behula to have her father-

in-law worship them. Overjoyed at the return of his wealth and sons, Chando Saudagar agreed to worship the Vishahari sisters, but with the condition that he would only use his left hand, as his right hand was dedicated to Lord Shiva. Since then, the five Manasha deities have been worshipped on Earth.

Enchanting Themes and Vibrant Styles of the Paintings:

The Manjusha is a square structure crafted from paper or thermocol sheets and bamboo sticks, with a pyramid-like top reminiscent of a traditional char-bangla house. The paintings on the Manjusha are inspired by the *Gatha* and are depicted in line drawings. On the walls of the Manjusha, the painter (often a purahit) illustrates the story of Behula, featuring her with snakes in her hands. Lakhindra is shown resting on Behula's lap. Common figurines include Behula holding snakes, Behula alongside Tunhi (demons), and Behula with Natula, where clothing is depicted hanging behind them.

I

II

Figure 1.C: The Vishahari temple within the complex of Mahasai Deorhi (I); Pandit ji of the temple discussed the story with us.

The majority of the paintings feature various forms of snakes: floating on water, three-headed snakes beside Behula, and a five-headed snake next to Lakhindra's lifeless body. Other images include the moon, trees, vessels, the sun, fish, bamboo, elephants, cats, and gardens (Figure 3.B). Stylistically, these paintings are divided into two categories: (I) those created up to the latter half of the 20th century and (II) those made more recently (Figure 3. A). The style of contemporary paintings differs significantly from earlier works. In the 20th century, figures were outlined in black and represented traditionally, resembling designs seen in family events such as marriages or

pujas. These traditional paintings often featured pinched noses, thin and narrow pointed hands and legs (Figure 3), with hair depicted using black lines, and large, arched eyes. The bodies of the figures were filled with red, green, and yellow colours, typically derived from locally available rocks and minerals (Figure 3 C), with white backgroundsⁱⁱⁱ. These can be considered "household paintings," commonly created by women performing the Manasha puja, akin to "*alpana*" seen in rural Bengal, Bihar, and Odisha. In contrast, contemporary paintings have been influenced by modern art and commercial trading (Figure 3.D). While the traditional themes are preserved, the style has evolved. Modern paintings feature outlines in fine green and bodies filled with sophisticated red, green, and yellow colours. Figures are depicted in well-decorated modern attire, including dhotis, stylish footwear, well-maintained moustaches, and fashionable hairstyles with a projected lock of hair (*chaitanna*). Artists now paint on various surfaces such as sarees, handkerchiefs, and even on the walls of houses for occasions like *Chhat* Puja and other local festivals (Figure 3. E).

A

B

C

D

E

Figure 3: Style of older paintings: A. Painting in black and red colour showing Behula and snakes; B. In colour painting showing Behula and snakes; C. Behula dancing in front of Siva; D. Snake goddess; E. Behula holding snakes with another goddess.

Evolution of Research on Manjusha Paintings:

In 1998, J. C. Sharma, an artist from Champanagar, published a seminal book titled *Manjusha Chitrakala* (Sharma 2010), which marked the first serious attempt to explore the history behind Manjusha paintings. Sharma linked these paintings with the ancient Janapada, though his analysis did not fully account for the ancient geography and history of the region. He associated the Manjusha paintings with antiquities such as terracotta figurines, stone sculptures, floral decorations, and decorated snake hoods discovered at the ancient mound of Champa, relating them to the well-known Vishahari *Gatha*. Following Sharma's work, several historians have shown interest in the theme of these paintings. R.K. Sinha and O.P. Pandey (Sinha and Pandey 2012) examined the paintings in the context of their historical and cultural significance. B.L. Chaudhury (Chaudhury 2013) and S.S. Parijeet (Parijeet 2018) also contributed to the study of Manjusha paintings, although their articles largely reiterated earlier findings. Rajiva Kumar Sinha, in his book *Manjusha Art: Reflections in Folklore, Trade, and Religious History*, situated these paintings in the early formation stages of states and linked them to the *Jataka* stories. Sinha proposed that the paintings evolved over generations and were compiled in written form in the nineteenth or twentieth century. He also suggested that the character of Chando was situated in the ancient Anga Janapada. The work of Chaudhury and Parijeet largely built upon previous research, presenting similar interpretations and insights into the Manjusha paintings.

A

B

C

D

E

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F

G

Figure 3.A: Image showing Bihula holding snakes in her hand along with chnado and his wife (A); a deity is drawn with the style of Manjusha painting(C);Behula with snakes (B): female deity in the Manusha painting (D); Bihula and Lakhindra in the bashar ghar (E); floral decoration (F); wedding ceremony of Bihula and Lakhindra (G).

Research Problems and Methodological Strategies:

Due to biases, the effects of regionalization, and limited knowledge of antiquarians, researchers have occasionally formulated theories and ideas about Manjusha paintings that are not fully credible. Previous research monographs and articles have inadequately revealed the history behind these paintings. They often neglect the ancient geography of the region and fail to consider contexts beyond current political boundaries. Stories and traditions from peripheral regions have also been overlooked in these studies. In contrast, this study undertook an extensive survey, engaging with individuals across the region who have knowledge of the paintings. It included the discovery of old photographs of these paintings and documentation of the Vishahari Puja ritual, which are crucial for a comparative analysis of contemporary paintings. Additionally, all associated *Gathas* and myths have been meticulously examined to provide a comprehensive understanding of the Manjusha paintings.

A

B

Figure 3.B: Depiction of a tree in Manjusha painting (A); vessels with traders (B).

The Role of Bhagalpur's Geography in Historical Context:

The area is situated on the fringe of the middle Ganga Valley. During the early medieval period, particularly under the Pala Empire, this region was part of the Pala dominion. Following this, it came under the control of the Sena Dynasty. Archaeological findings from Vikramashila, along with inscriptions from Masanikesa and Sahura, indicate that during this time, Campa was a prominent city in this geographical region. During the Muslim period, the area was governed by the Bengal Sultans and later came under Mughal control. In the early British era, it was part of the Bengal Presidency. The geographical location of Bhagalpur has played a crucial role in understanding the history of the region. In the Sultanate period, eastern India experienced significant upheaval, marked by widespread anarchy. Established traditional institutions were dismantled, leading to drastic changes in education, culture, and morality throughout the late medieval period. This tumultuous phase gave rise to numerous superstitions as people sought

explanations for daily hardships—such as snake bites, tiger attacks, cholera, typhoid, and famines—believing these misfortunes to be the result of curses from previous lives. Consequently, they turned to supernatural explanations for relief. The decline in ethics, education, and mental clarity during this period led to the emergence of new deities and *Gathas* (hymns) dedicated to these gods. This era saw the development of a new cosmogony distinct from traditional Sanskrit literature. The *Gathas*, composed to praise various deities, are known as "Mangal Kavya." It was believed that reciting these verses, especially in the Mangal Raga (a musical mode associated with auspicious occasions), would bring both spiritual and material benefits. These songs were traditionally performed from one Mangal Bar (Tuesday) to the next, reflecting the deep cultural significance of these rituals in providing hope and solace to the people.

Figure 3.C: Chnado (Chand Saudagar) in various postures.

The Role of Mangal Kavya in Folklore and Religious Practice:

Mangal Kavya refers to a group of Hindu religious texts composed between the 13th and 18th centuries A.D., featuring narratives of indigenous deities. Among the major Mangal Kavyas are Chandi Mangal, dedicated to Goddess Chandi; Manasha Mangal, centred on Goddess Manasha; and Dharma Mangal, pertaining to God Dharmaraja. Additionally, there are several minor Mangal Kavyas, including Shivaya Mangal, Kalika Mangal, Raya Mangal, Shashti Mangal, Shitala Mangal, and Kamala Mangal. Each of these texts was composed by one or more poets, who were typically devotees of the respective deities. These texts hold significant cultural and religious importance in the Hindu households of Bengal, Bangladesh, Assam, and Odisha, where the deities

featured in the Mangal Kavyas are worshipped on specific days, known as "Bar," during particular seasons. During these rituals, the *Gathas* (hymns) composed for each deity are chanted. A traditional aspect of the worship involves creating *alpana*, which are paintings made with a white paste of rice flour mixed with water. The themes of these *alpanas* often depict the myths and stories described in the Mangal *Kavyas*, providing a visual narration of the deities' tales and enhancing the ritualistic practices.

A

B

Figure 3.E: (A) An artist is painted a temporary well made for Chhat Puja. (B) Courtyard of a house is painted in the style of the Manjusha Painting.

A

B

Figure 3.D: Painting promoted for business purpose. A; students are taught Manjusha painting. B: An exhibition on Manjusha painting for business purpose.

Exploring Manasha Mangal: Hymns and Rituals:

Manasamangal *Kavya* is the oldest and most popular among the Mangal *Kavyas*, detailing how the snake-goddess Manasa established her worship on earth by converting a worshipper of Shiva. Manasa, an ancient non-Aryan deity, was worshipped in Bengal long before the arrival of Aryans. It is believed that she came to Bengal with the Dravidians, who venerated her for protection against snakes (Figure 8). Manasa is also known by other names such as Bisahari, Janguli, and Padmava. The narrative of Manasamangal begins with the conflict between the merchant Chandradhar (or

Chand Sadagar) and Manasa, and concludes with Chandradhar becoming a devoted follower of the goddess. Chandradhar, a renowned and prosperous trader from Champanagar, initially rejects Manasa, refusing to even acknowledge her as a deity. In retaliation, Manasa destroys seven of his ships at sea and kills his seven sons. However, the newly-wed wife of Chand's youngest son, Lakhindar, named Behula, uses her strength of character, boundless courage, and deep devotion to win over Manasa. Through her devotion, Behula manages to revive Chand's seven sons and recover the lost ships. Only after these feats does Behula return home. The earliest known poet of this genre in medieval Bengali literature was Kana Haridatta (circa 13th century), although his work has not survived. His name appears in the writings of Bijay Gupta and Purushottam. Subsequent poets who composed versions of Manasamangal include Purushottam, Narayan Deb (circa 15th century), Bijay Gupta, and Bipradas Pipilai. Among these, Bijay Gupta's *Manasamangal* (or *Padmapuran*) (1484-85) is particularly notable for its literary richness. Bipradas Pipilai's *Manasabijay* (1495-96) was also composed during this period. Narayan Deb's version is also known as *Padmapuran*. Later poets in this tradition include Ketakadas Kshemananda (circa 17th century), Jagajjiban Ghoshal (circa 17th century), and Jibankrishna Maitra (circa 18th century).

Figure 8: Scene from Manasha Mangal (Photo Courtesy: Internet Archive).

Exploring the Link Between Manasha Mangal and Behula Vishahari:

The Manasha Mangal and the Behula Vishahari *Gatha* are closely related texts, with only a few notable differences. In Manasha Mangal, it is stated that Behula was born from a lotus stalk by Shiva, while the Vishahari *Gatha* describes six Vishahari sisters born from Shiva's lock. Upon closer examination, there are inconsistencies in the Vishahari *Gatha* compared to the Manasha Mangal, including a lack of continuity and some lines that do not precisely align with the main story. Both tales mention several places and *ghats*, which are largely similar, although there are minor differences in names and descriptions. Notably, both narratives conclude with Behula's journey ending at Tribeni *Ghat*, located on the banks of the Ganga in the Hooghly district of West Bengal. In the Manasha Mangal, Behula travels from Champanagar to Tribeni using a banana tree boat called a Bhela, propelled by the Ganga's current through various *ghats* (Figure 9). The place "Champaknagar" mentioned in both stories has yet to be definitively identified. Some scholars suggest that Champaknagar might be a location 8 km north of Mahasthangarh and 10 km north of Bogura in modern Bangladesh. In contrast, L.N. Dey and B.C. Law propose that Champaknagar could be the ancient site referred to in the Manasha Mangal. It is likely that the written accounts of Manasha Mangal and the Vishahari *Gatha* share a common origin, with the variations resulting from alterations and additions over their long transmission since the 12th-13th centuries.

JHAM

A

B

Figure 9: Image of Behula and Lakhindar is made during the time of Manasha Puja in ruler Bengal (Photo Courtesy: Social Media).

General Observations: Comprehensive Insights into the Study's Findings and Implications:

Now, it can be said that these paintings, which are a result of a well-known *gatha*, are nothing new but the same story described in *Manasha Mangal*. On one hand, it can be difficult to find out the exact history behind this story. On the other hand, the place Champanagar could not be identified easily with Chand Saudagar's "Champaknagar". In this article, an attempt has been made to reveal facts that are embedded within the paintings and the *gathas*. The following observations can be made after analysing all the aspects minutely:

1. First of all, the ancient geography of this region must be studied carefully. In the 9th-12th century, before *Manasha Mangal* was composed, this region was under the political supremacy of Gauda. Even during the colonial period, it was a part of the Bengal presidency. We all know the story of Rajlakshmi-Srikanta, which is also considered a biography of the famous Bengali poet Sarat Chandra Chattopadhyay. From this story, we know about the childhood of this writer who lived in his maternal uncle's house and taught there in the Durgacharan School in Champanagar. He spent most of his childhood with Indranath fishing in the river Ganga and travelling by boat. His maternal uncle's house and Durgacharan School are still there. Another famous Bengali poet, Bibhutibhusan Bandyopadhyay, also spent time in this town. A house of his is still standing in the middle of the town. Even today, a Bengali library and several Bengali organizations can be found. As a part of Bengal, this region was once a stronghold of the Bengali communities and witnessed sophisticated Bengali literature and living styles. In the 19th-20th century, two famous Bengali novelists composed their novels centring on this place. Thus, the possibility of the *Manasha Mangal* story centring on the town Champanagar cannot be discarded completely.
2. The district Gazetteer of Byrne (Byrne 1911) and Chaudhury (Chaudhury 1962) deal with the existing cultures of this district elaborately. They mentioned the tradition of the

Manasha Puja and the *gatha* of the Vishahari. The works of K.K. Datta repeated the same cultural tradition (Chaudhury 1962, 278). We had discussed with the family members of the oldest settled family of this region, i.e., Mahasai Deorhi. This oldest Bengali Zamindar family was settled here in the 14th-15th century CE and has practiced Manasha puja since that time in a particular place. The present head of the family told us an interesting story and showed a small square temple plastered with thick lime mortar. The bricks of the temple are older than the Lakhari one, which is situated on the ruins of the ancient Champanagar not more than 50 m south of the present channel of the Ganga. They believed this temple to be the temple of Chand Saudagar where he first worshipped the Goddess Manasha. A 78-year-old Pandit of the temple told us that he has worshipped here on the occasion of Manasha Puja since 1960. They have decorated the temple premises with *alpana* on that occasion but have not painted any such paintings within the temple premises. Therefore, it is difficult to find out a particular time when and where these paintings were drawn on the surface of Manjusha. It is also difficult to postulate with certainty that the tradition of this painting has continued since the medieval period when Manasha Mangal was composed. But it can be safely mentioned that probably it was a ritualistic painting painted by a handful of people in society on the wall of Manjusha in black and white colour in the way of naturalistic representation of the *gatha*, same as *alpana* is drawn with a specific theme during different pujas in rural Bengal.

Figure 10: Location of Mahasthan garh, Champanagar, and Tribeni ghat.

3. The *gatha* is chanted during the puja of Vishahari (Manasha). Unlike the novel "Manasha Mangal," it is passed down orally through generations. This oral transmission likely led to variations and additions over time. The facts of the *gatha* cannot be easily distinguished from the story of "Manasha Mangal," suggesting that a version of this tale lived among the Bengali communities in this area and later spread to other regions.
4. In all the stories, the boat (Bhela) of Behula is said to have floated down the Ganga's powerful currents, ending its journey at Tribeni Ghat after six months. There is no direct connection between Mahathangarh and Tribeni. Tribeni is situated on the bank of the Ganga, approximately 500 km southwest of Mahathangarh, which is located on the bank of the Brahmaputra. On the other hand, Tribeni is 410 km south of Bhagalpur, also on the

same river. It is plausible for a boat or Bhela to cover such a distance in six months with the help of the river's natural flow (Figure 10). A place called Ujani is found opposite the Ganga, beside the river Kosi, which locals claim to be Behula's birthplace. However, the historical accuracy of this story is questionable. It was likely the imagination of a poet during a dark period in Indian history when people, fearing snakes, turned to supernatural beliefs rather than scientific solutions. The devotion of a woman to her husband resonated with society, making Behula a beloved figure, particularly in eastern India.

5. The poet's imagination was not entirely baseless. Champa was a significant city in ancient Indian history and flourished during the early medieval period. It had a vast hinterland with agricultural fields and forest products. Medieval texts mention trade items like goats, bananas, corn, sandalwood, and betel leaf with Kalinga, Patna, Devpur, Mathura, and other contemporary cities. No other city named Champa reached such prominence, except for Champanagar in Bhagalpur. It is reasonable to postulate that the imaginary character of Chand Saudagar, created by Kana Haridatta in the 13th century C.E., was likely centered around this ancient city of Champanagar.

Notes

ⁱ It is made of light materials, i.e., paper, soft wood, and shola or thermocol sheet, so that it can easily be flow on the water.

ⁱⁱ Told by the 78 years old Pandit of the Old Behula-Vishahari temple of the Nathnagar (Figure 1C).

ⁱⁱⁱ A 78 years old Pandit, a 75 years old local photographer (Ajit Kumar Jhar), and Shiv Shankar Parjeet, Former Deputy Director of PRD, told us that the family of Mahasai Deorhi which is one of the oldest Jamindar family and still they have maintained their royal status. This family settled here in the time of Emperor Akbar and collected local revenue on the behalf of the Mughal Emperor. This family of Campānagar have practiced these painting since a long time generation by generation during the time of Vishahari puja in their ancestral temple within the complex of Mahasai Deorhi (Figure 1C).

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